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Utilization of Sediment Activities of Straight-Net Craps as Organic Fertilizer Substitution Material, In Lake Tondano, Minahasa Regency, North Sulawesi Province

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Abstract.

The purpose of this study was to determine the fish feed waste that causes pollution of the waters of Lake Tondano and to determine the nutrients contained in the sediment of Lake Tondano which can be used as organic fertilizer. Utilization of sediment from net cage cultivation activities as organic fertilizer to reduce pollution and prevent siltation. Cultivation activities of straight nets that take place continuously and an increase in the number of caged nets which do not pay attention to the sustainability of the sustainable environment of Lake Tondano, this affects the existence and function of Lake Tondano as a place to meet human needs. In the end, it has an impact on the economic income of the coastal community of Lake Tondano. Sources of data were obtained from questionnaires given to groups of existing farmers, besides the questionnaires, interviews were also conducted with farmers and government officials to obtain information about the impact of fish farming activities on the environment of Lake Tondano, more specifically on sediment accumulation in Lake Tondano. This research is one solution to minimize pollution in Lake Tondano so that Lake Tondano can be used according to its designation in the long term. The results showed that the Lake Tondano Sediment contains a lot of nutrients that can be used as organic fertilizer. Elements of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium and Calcium contained in the sediments of Lake Tondano. can be used as the basis for an organic fertilizer formula.

Keywords: Sediment, Organic Fertilizer, Lake Tondano.

Introduction

The Lake Tondano is one of the water resource assets in North Sulawesi Province. Lake Tondano is multi-functional in which it can be used by the lake's coastal communities, among others, for agriculture, animal husbandry, hydropower, PDAM, tourism and fisheries. The problem that exists in Lake Tondano is that the current condition is very alarming where the natural state of Lake Tondano has shifted to an unsustainable Lake Tondano environment.

The presence of water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) contributes to sedimentation in the lake which results in silting. The rapid growth of water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) so that at a certain time this plant will die and the rest of this plant is thrown into the lake so that it accumulates at the bottom which causes eutrophication and lake sedimentation. In addition to waste from dead plants, there is also caged net cage waste in the form of leftover feed that is wasted into Lake Tondano.

In 2013 the total organic waste of feed in the rearing of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in the cultivation of fixed net cages was 10,874 units and the total feeding of 17,240.13 tons produced 11,403 organic waste. 13 tons (Kusen, D. 2014).

The negative impact of all these activities causes sedimentation in Lake Tondano. In 1934 the depth reached 40 m after 47 years later the depth changed to 20 m (Sittadewi, 2008) and research by the Environment Agency of North Sulawesi Province, (2011) the average depth of Lake Tondano is only 12 m.

Sedimentation are: (1). The entry of sediment loads into a certain aquatic environment through water media and deposited in that environment, (2). Soil or part of the land that is transported by water from an eroded place in a watershed (DAS) and enters a body of water. Sediment will be deposited in a place where the water velocity slows down or stops.

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This depositional event is known as a sedimentation event or process (Arsyad, 2006). The occurrence of sedimentation in the waters of Lake Tondano is a complex problem from existing activities along the Watershed (DAS) as well as activities that take place within the environment itself. Potentially, the impact of fish farming waste disposal in floating net cages, which are rich in nutrients and organic matter, can increase sedimentation, siltation, hypoxia, hypereutrophication and changes in productivity and structure of benthic communities. Based on the movement mechanism, sediment transport is divided into: (1). Floating sediment transport/suspension sediment, is a sediment particle that moves to float in the water and is carried away by the flow of the river, (2). Transport of bottom sediment/bed load, is a sediment particle that moves not far from the riverbed and moves in shifts, creeps, rolls or jumps.

Sedimentation that exists along the shores of Lake Tondano, namely the destruction of forests in the upstream part into agricultural areas and community plantations along the borders of rivers that empties into Lake Tondano causes erosion. Sedimentation can also be caused by activities that take place in the lake water environment, namely the cultivation of floating net cages, where the remaining waste from these activities enters and settles on the bottom of the water. The negative impact of all these activities causes sedimentation in Lake Tondano. In 1934 the depth reached 40 m after 47 then the depth changed to 20 m (Sittadewi, 2008).

Fish farming using floating net cages has been scientifically tested through a series of studies to increase nitrogen and phosphorus nutrients. The amount of nitrogen and phosphorus polluting the waters by floating net cages can be determined based on primary data on measurements of total nitrogen and phosphorus in fish meat produced by floating net cages and the nitrogen and phosphorus content of the feed used. Siltation is caused by several factors, including erosion. In addition, the uncontrolled presence of water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) also increases the rate of siltation. Water hyacinth plants (*Eichhornia crassipes*) that die will sink and accumulate at the bottom of the lake.

Organic fertilizers are fertilizers that are composed of living things, such as weathering the remains of plants, animals and humans. Organic fertilizers can be in the form of solid or liquid which are used to improve the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil. Organic fertilizer contains more organic matter than its nutrient content. Nutrients in organic fertilizers:

Among other things, Nitrogen or N is a nutrient in the soil that plays a very important role in plant growth. The supply of N through fertilization is very necessary because N is the element that is mostly lost from the land after harvesting. Phosphorus or P where the element P is an important substance but is usually always in a state of deficiency in the soil. Elemental P is very important as a source of energy because it lacks element P greatly inhibits plant growth and metabolic reactions. Calcium in the absorption of water is greatly assisted by calcium, in plants calcium plays a role in activating the growth of root hairs and seeds as well as strengthening stems and potassium functions in the formation of proteins and carbohydrates, besides that potassium also functions as plant antibodies to fight disease.

Material And Methods

The research was conducted in Eris Village, Eris District, Minahasa Regency, North Sulawesi Province. Eris Village has a high net cage when compared to the villages along the Lake Tondano Coast.

The method used in this research is descriptive exploration method, laboratory test. Descriptive exploration method was conducted to obtain information about the state of the net cages operating in Lake Tondano, Eris Village, Eris District, Minahasa Regency, North Sulawesi Province. analyzed using the Schmittou method (1991) to calculate the amount of organic waste, nitrogen and phosphorus produced by floating net cage activities. The results of the analysis from the Manado Standardization Research Institute Laboratory (BARISTAND) are the elements Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Calcium and Potassium.

Results and Discussion

1. Condition of the Waters of Lake Tondano

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The use of Lake Tondano by residents for the cultivation of floating net cages, assessed in terms of aesthetics and the environment has greatly decreased, where the layout between the floating net cage units is irregular and the distance between the floating net cage units is only 1 m. Mantau (2010), stated that basically the placement of floating net cages should be at a minimum water depth ranging from 2 - 3 m and an optimal depth of 5 - 7 m with a water brightness of 1 - 2 m. In addition, another problem is the silting of Lake Tondano, so that the placement of floating net cages is getting closer to the middle of the waters.

The rapid eutrophication of the lake is believed by many researchers to be triggered by human activities that use the water body as an area for fish production in excessive floating net cages. To prevent excessive eutrophication due to this phenomenon, the maximum floating net cage setting is only 1% of the lake surface area and the distance between the floating net cages is 50 m (Zahidah, 2007). The area profile of the floating net cage unit above proves that the cultivation of floating net cages in Eris Village is very influential on the aesthetics and sustainability of Lake Tondano. This situation has an impact on the income of cultivators to meet the necessities of life.

2. Lake Tondano Fish Cultivation Activities

The development of fish farming activities in Lake Tondano from year to year tends to increase, this situation provides an illustration that the need for nutritious food is very much needed by the population and increases the income of farmers. According to Ndahawali (2002) the number of floating net cages in 2000 was 2,078 units. The latest development in 2021 the number of floating net cages operating is 11,003 units, besides that there are also floating net cages that are damaged this is due to changes in water quality conditions (aer lewo) which result in mass fish deaths so that farmers experience material losses.

The special production of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in floating net cages in each village along the coast of Lake Tondano in 2021 differs in the amount of production per year. This difference corresponds to the number of floating net cage units. The total number of units of floating net cages for rearing tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in 2021 is 11,003 units spread over 14 villages along the shores of Lake Tondano. The distribution of the number of floating net cages are: Touliang Oki Village there are 203 units (production of 434.83 tons); Ranomerut Village 175 units (production 374.85 tons); Tandengan Village 463 units (production 991.75 tons); Village Tandengan 1 as many as 286 units (production 604.04 tons); Eris Village 3,756 units (production 8,045.35 tons); Watumea Village 966 units (production 2069.17 tons); Telap Village 1,157 units (production 2478.29 tons); Toulimembet village 2,071 units (production 4,436.08 tons); Kaweng Village 280 units (production 599.76 tons); Paslaten Village 388 units (831.10 tons production); Tounolet Village 507 units (production 1,085.99 tons); Timu Sendangan Village 43 units (92.11 tons production); Talikuran Village 338 units (production 724.00 tons) and Urongo Village 245 units (524.79 production).

Production of floating net cages in 2021, for rearing tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) along the coast of Lake Tondano as many as 10,874 units resulted in the production of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) of 23,292.11 tons with an average harvest size of 350 g (1kg/3 fish). The highest production is found in Eris Village with 3,756 units (production 8,045.35 tons) compared to 13 other villages.

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Figure 1. Net cages in Lake Tondano : (1). PDAM, (2). The road to the floating net cage, (3). Guard house, (4). Apu-grass (*Pitsia stratiotes*) cover the Karamba unit

3. Feed Composition Used

Floating net cage cultivation is an intensive cultivation system in terms of feed because during rearing Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) requires artificial feed for growth to reach optimal size. The types of feed commonly used in Eris Village are type A feed, type B feed and type C feed with a dose of 3% of body weight. The percentage of use of these 3 feeds which is the most widely used is Type A, because type A feed has an agent in Toulimembet Village which is adjacent to Eris Village. The availability of this feed provides benefits for farmers who do not incur transportation costs to buy feed elsewhere.

The results of the proximate test analysis of 3 types of feed A, type B and type of feed C were given to tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) there were differences in the composition of nutritional content from the results obtained the protein content of feed type A (28.86%); type of feed B (29.69%); type of feed C (27.98 %), nitrogen content of feed type A (4.62%); type of feed B (4.75%); type of feed C (4.48%) and phosphorus content of feed type A (1.62%); type of feed B (1.27%) and type of feed C (1.28%). From the results of the proximate test, the percentage of protein compared to protein in feed type A, feed type B and type C feed, it turns out that the value of phosphorus content in feed type A is higher than feed type B and type C feed (Kusen D, 2014).

There is no physical difference in the form of A type of feed, type of feed and type of feed C, but after doing experiments in the laboratory the solubility of feed type B and type C feed is lower than feed type A

Table 1. Composition of Types of Feed A, B and C given to Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

No	Parameter	Analysis Results			Method
		A	B	C	
1.	Moisture content	9,67	10,31	10,47	Oven
2.	Ash content	9,18	10,00	7,74	Gravimetric
3.	Crude fiber	3,16	6,68	4,76	Gravimetric
4.	Fat	6,43	7,05	7,47	Extraction
5.	Protein	28,86	29,69	27,98	Makrokedahl
6.	Carbohydrate	42,70	36,27	41,51	Calculations
7.	Nitrogen	4,62	4,75	4,48	Makrokedahl
8.	Phosphorus	1,62	1,27	1,28	Spectrophotometer

Source: Proximate Test analysis results (Kusen D, 2014)

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Murtidjo (2001), stated the percentage composition of commercial feed protein (18-26), water content (10-12), crude fiber (5-6), and ash content (6). The percentage of type A feed from the proximate analysis of protein content (28.86), ash content (9.18), when compared with the composition of freshwater fish culture feed, (Murtidjo, 2001) the results showed significant differences in protein (18-26%) and ash content (6%). Eco-friendly feed means that it does not have a major impact on environmental changes.

4. Nutrient Content in Lake Tondano Sediments

Fish farming using floating net cages has been scientifically tested through a series of studies to increase nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) nutrients in lake sediments. Lake sediments also contain many other nutrients, namely potassium (K) and calcium (Ca). These elements are some of the elements that are needed in making organic fertilizers. The results of laboratory analysis showed that the concentrations of the elements Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K) and Calcium (Ca) in Lake Tondano sediments as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Concentration of elements in Lake Tondano sedimen sediments

No	Parameter	Unit	Station			Test Method
			I	II	III	
1	Nitrogen (N)	%	0,26	0,20	0,21	SNI01-2986-1992 Item 5.5
2	Phosphorus(P)	%	0,48	1,51	2,69	SNI 2803-2012-2012 Item 6.3
3	Potassium (K)	ppm	251,59	416,84	401,44	SNI 01-2896-1998
4	Calcium(Ca)	ppm	236,82	714,23	2268,69	SNI 01-2896-1998

Source: Manado Institute of Industrial Research and Standardization (Baristand, 2021)

4.1 Nutrient Content of Nitrogen (N)

Data on the nitrogen content of nutrients that have been taken from the coastal area of Lake Tondano, Eris Village, Eris District, Minahasa Regency are shown in Figure 1. Laboratory results from samples taken from 3 (three) stations are; Station I on the coast of the lake (0.26), Station II in the tancap net cage area (0.20) and Station III (0.21). The highest nitrogen content of the three stations is located at station I (0.26), while the lowest nitrogen content is at station II (0.20).

Figure 2. Nitrogen Content in Lake Tondano Sediments

The highest nitrogen content occurs due to the entry of organic matter and feces of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and the rest of the feed that is not consumed into Lake Tondano or in other words, the higher the rate of decomposition of organic matter in the sediment, the more nitrogen content is produced. According to Evans (1987) organic matter sourced from fecal pellets such as fish manure is classified as high in nutritional value and easy to decompose.

4.2 Nutrient Content of Phosphorus (P)

Phosphorus nutrient content data that has been taken from the coastal area of Lake Tondano, Eris Village, Eris District, Minahasa Regency is shown in Figure 2. The results of the phosphorus test from samples

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taken from 3 (three) stations are; Station I (0.48), Station II (1.51) and Station III (2.69). The highest phosphorus content of the three stations is located at station III (2.69), station II (1.51), while the lowest phosphorus content is at station I (0.48).

Figure 3. Phosphorus Content in Lake Tondano Sediments

According to Suyanto (1998), feces and fish feed that are wasted into the water have an impact on increasing organic matter, nitrogen and phosphate, meaning that the more activities of floating net cages, the more feed that is not consumed by fish and accumulates at the bottom of the water. In addition, due to albilitum feeding (continuous until the fish are full), the consequence of this phenomenon is that the phosphate level in the sediment increases. The total phosphorus waste in 2013 that was wasted in Lake Tondano increased based on the number of units of tilapia floating net cages (10,874 units), Phosphorus waste in the sediment produced was 108.61 tons, so an average of 9.0 tons per month.

4.3 Content of Potassium (K)

Data on the nutrient content of Potassium (K) contained in the sediment of Lake Tondano in Eris Village is shown in Figure 4. Laboratory results from samples taken from 3 (three) stations are; Station I on the coast of the lake (251.59 ppm), Station II in the tancap net cage area (416.84 ppm) and Station III (401.44 ppm). The highest Potassium (K) content of the three stations is located at station II (416.84), while the lowest Potassium content is at station I (251.59).

Figure 4. Content of Potassium (K) in Lake Tondano . Sediments

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The nutrient content of Potassium (K) above shows that high potassium elements are found at station II, where the location is an area of tancap net cage cultivation.

4.4 Calcium (Ca) Content

Data on the nutrient content of Calcium (Ca) contained in the sediment of Lake Tondano in Eris Village is shown in Figure 5. Laboratory results from samples taken from 3 (three) stations are; Station I on the coast of the lake (236.82 ppm), Station II in the net cage area (714.23 ppm) and Station III (2268.69 ppm). The highest calcium (Ca) content of the three stations is located at station III (2268.69 ppm), while the lowest calcium content is at station I (236.82 ppm).

Figure 5. Calcium (Ca) content in the Tondano . Sediment

Elements of Calcium (Ca) are found in the waters of Lake Tondano naturally because the waters of Lake Tondano have net cage cultivation activities. The element of calcium is found in the fins and scales of tilapia fish, of which the calcium content is the most abundant in the fins of tilapia. The element of calcium found in tilapia fish scales is 4.98 mg/l while in tilapia fish fins it is 33.33 mg/l (Tiwow. et al, 2016).

5. Presence of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium and Calcium as Organic Fertilizer Ingredients

Lake Tondano sediments contain many nutrients that can be used as organic fertilizers. The results of this study provide data where the elements Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium and Calcium are present in the sediment of Lake Tondano. The presence of these four elements in the sediment of Lake Tondano can be used as the basis for formulating organic fertilizers.

The existing organic fertilizers are derived from: animal manure, household waste residues and wastes derived from the skins of fruits and vegetables. Utilization of Lake Tondano sediment for organic fertilizer is a good step to minimize the silting of Lake Tondano if carried out on a large scale. Utilization of Lake Tondano sediment to be used as organic fertilizer has a good impact on the sustainability of Lake Tondano.

Conclusion

1. Lake Tondano sediments contain a lot of nutrients that can be used as organic fertilizers.
2. Elements of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium and Calcium are found in the sediments of Lake Tondano. Can be used as the basis for an organic fertilizer formula.

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